

The HR Practices and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

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Abstract

A considerable amount of studies showed a positive approach towards HR practices and organizational effectiveness, but the research regarding the importance of the association between HR practices and organizational citizenship behavior remains scarce. This study, therefore, aimed to examine the relationship between selected HR practices including recruitment & selection, training & development, and compensation & benefit and organizational citizenship behavior. A quantitative method was employed to collect the data in which 251 employees were being participated through the snowball sampling technique with all aspects. Data were analyzed using the statistical software package SPSS 20. The results found a positive relationship between HR practices and organizational citizenship behavior. Moreover, training and development have the greatest deal of streamlines to improve organizational citizenship behavior.

Key Words: *HR Practices, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Performance effectiveness*

INTRODUCTION

The way of today's working environment is considerably more intricate and unexpected than at any other time. After the introduction of globalization, privatization and liberalization, the opposition in the business situation has increased in multifold (Itishree Gita Kumari & Rabindra Kumar Pradhan, 2014) where excessiveness to knowledge and consciousness from employees has produced uttermost competition among the organizations. In such a contemporary world, organizations particularly chemical industries facing a grievous challenging environment; thus seeking for the dynamic changes in order to develop and maintain an optimum level of competitiveness by springing up a high commitment for employees with HR practices (Asim Mukhtar et al., 2012). The HR practices including (recruitment & selection, training & development, and compensation & benefit) play an important and demanding role to rejuvenate the organization culture where employees incline to show an optimum and beyond the optimum level of performance through their citizenship behavior (Koster & Sander, 2006). Various studies have come across to examine the relationships of HR practices with different kinds of employee behaviors, however, OCB is one of the salient features of the employee to enhance co-worker performance and improve organizational effectiveness.

Over a decade human resource practices entail greater significance in fostering organization success through its major participation and discretionary efforts (Li-Yun Sun, Samuel Aryee, & Kenneth S. Law, 2007). Recent studies show that HR practices have an enormous deal of flexibility to shape the employee's attitude in terms of their citizenship behavior towards organizational effectiveness (Asim Mukhtar et al., 2012). Citizenship refers to an unrestricted type of behavior in which employees provoke to do something positive, constructive, and creative to support their co-workers and benefit the organization (Wright & Boswell, 2002). The role of human resource practices has created an immense capacity for employees to adopt organizational citizenship behavior to achieve organizational objectives. The term organizational citizenship behavior defined by (Podsakoff, 2000) as "individual behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization. By discretionary, we mean that the behavior is not an enforceable requirement of the role or the job description, that is, the clearly specifiable terms of the person's employment contract with the organization; the behavior is rather a matter of personal choice, such that its omission is not generally understood as punishable (pp. 513-563)."

The role of HR practices widely influenced on employee behavior particularly their citizenship behavior in which if organization displays a recognition policy where employees work recognized by their supervisor then they will be inclined to do more than they officially required, similarly empowerment exercises facilitate employees to feel sense of ownership and develop ability to manipulate over work (Asim Mukhtar et al., 2012). Consequently employee commitment with work will likely increase to in greater extent to accomplish the

organizational goals. The HR practices also play a crucial role in promoting the effective functioning of the organization (Jiing Li-Farh, Chen-Bo Zhong, & Dennis W. Organ, 2008). Recent studies provided evidence that as outcomes of HR practices, employees incline to involve in extra-role behavior, shows citizenship and pro-social behavior, and effectively control the related overall performance (Van Dyne & Le-Pine, 2000).

This study therefore, aims to understand the association between HR practices and organizational citizenship behavior. The main purpose of this study is to analyze how HR practices including recruitment & selection, training & development, and compensation & benefit contribute to shaping the employee attitude towards organizational citizenship behavior under the premises of the Pakistani chemical industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Present day organizations operate on work structures that are group-situated and self-governing instead of individualized and centrally controlled. This course of action has increased the significance of cooperation and activity among workers (Ilgen&Pulakos, 2000). The greater part of this has made optional behaviors like organizational citizenship is irreplaceable for organizations (LePine et al., 2002). Researchers and organizational managers have indicated high enthusiasm for organizational citizenship behavior (Hoffman et al., 2007) on the grounds that it identifies with vital organizational results like benefit (Koys, 2001). Presentation of such additional part behaviors that increase organizational objectives however are not unambiguously compensated or can't be completely assured, is a key confront for organizational leaders (Korsgaard et al., 2010).

(Gerben S et al., 2003) identified the fact that high-ranking of OCB is particularly profitable in multidisciplinary groups, in light of the fact that the complex and dynamic nature of the undertakings and the particular learning and ability of workfellows working in such group situations make it hard to indicate and control individual conduct. Interestingly and incomprehensibly, on the other hand, the proactive participation and activity that are features for OCB may be hard to acknowledge among co-workers with diverse instructive and useful foundations. In reality, a few researchers have noticed that distinctive individuals may hold inclinations and generalizations around each other, which posture issues identified with low group distinguishing proof and OCB (Neale & Kramer, 1999).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior - An Individual Perspective

Various studies have analyzed and posited the relation of OCB with individual role stressor (i.e. Role uncertainty, Role disagreement, Role overwork) in which (Russell E. Johnson, 2011) examined that why role stressors concern with OCB. Since they are seen as an obstacle to work accomplishment, role stressors, particularly vagueness and struggle, inspire negative feelings, which lessen the probability that OCB will be performed. Though positive feelings are connected to activity inclinations to perform prosaically and helpful practices; negative feelings are identified with a lower probability of participation (De Cremer & Van Hiel, 2006). Role stressors offer ascension to encounters of nervousness and pressure (Jackson & Schuler, 2001), two passionate states that are to the contrary identified with prosocial practices (M. B. Harris, 2002). Negative enthusiastic states may improve the probability of withdrawal from optional practices, as OCB (Bachrach & Jex, 2000), in light of the fact that they prompt redirection of a push to adapt to wellsprings of strain (Belschak & Den Hartog, 2009). Unpleasant shocks may even actuate behavioral hindrance frameworks, bringing about shirking focused motivations that "turn off" OCB (Johnson & Chang, 2008).

Western researchers focused on OCB in the context of extra-role behavior; which is however beyond the role behavior but essential to accomplish the organizational effectiveness (Jiing Li-Farh, Chen-Bo Zhong, & Dennis W. Organ, 2008). Organizational citizenship behavior also associated with the level of job involvement which includes qualities about the reputability of work or the significance of work in the remarkable value (Lodahl and Kejner, 2000). In that capacity people who show high association in their occupations consider their work to be an essential piece of their lives and regardless of whether they feel great about themselves is firmly identified with how they perform on their occupations. As such for profoundly included people

performing great at work is essential for their self-regard (Lodahl and Kejner, 2000). As a result this individual who is high in employment association truly distributes to and is worried about their work (Kanungo, 1999).

Linn Van Dyne and Jon L. Pierce (2004) emphasized on employee attitude with an aspect of their psychological ownership and possessive feelings to accomplish the task. In this regard several empirical studies have provided evidence that psychological ownership directly related to commitment and satisfaction to the cooperative and extra-role behavior (Pierce et al., 2001). The psychological contract holds an important and growing position to increase employment relationships at the workplace (William H. Turnley, 2003). The psychological contract usually paid attention to two areas, first one is loyalty and mutual understanding between employees and organization and the second one is employee attitude and behavior in terms of job satisfaction, commitment with work, and efforts beyond the standard mark leads and increases the OCB (Keeney & Svyantek, 2000). Moreover OCB has been viewed as an outcome of initiative and proactive behaviors are major factors to drive organizational effectiveness, particularly when engagement in work turns more flexible than ever before (Ning Li, Jian Liang, & J. Michael Crant, 2010). Proactive attitude push individuals to put forth their actions even in difficult circumstances and motivate them to anticipate in work more confidently and effectively which in return employee shows their citizenship behavior to support co-worker and benefit the organization (William & Turners, 2006). Therefore, organization competitiveness mainly reliance on employee activeness and a combination of management strategies and HRM practices (Dariusz Turek & Agnieszka Wojtczuk-Turek, 2015).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior - An Organizational Perspective

In recent literature (Kelly L. Zellars, Bennett J. Tepper, & Michelle K. Duffy, 2002) presented that the absence of OCB can create an antagonistic situation between supervisor and subordinate and consequently throughout the organization. Some supervisors perform practices that can be described as insulting, frustrating, undermining, or oppressive (Duffy, Ganster, and Pagon, 2002). The term abusive supervision refers to "subordinates' view of the degree to which their supervisors participate in the supported demo of threatening verbal and nonverbal practices, barring physical contact" (Tepper, 2000, p. 178). Manhandled subordinates report more life disappointment, goals to stop their occupations, part struggle, and mental misery, (Duffy et al., 2002), and that subordinates' view of shamefulness discloses their reactions to harsh supervision (Tepper, 2000). Consequently, harsh supervision speaks to a wellspring of unfairness that has genuine complications for organizations and workers (Bies and Tripp, 1998). Though (Asif Shahzavet.al., 2013) supported the relationship between employee and supervisor through the linkage of servant leadership and OCB with the mediating effect of trust. Leadership ever been a prominent concept for organization to influence others; however in today emerging organization leadership dramatically running its route through cooperation, mutual understanding, convey chance to subordinate to participate in decision making process, following teamwork, and provided the ground for moral and ethical behavior that ultimately created a element of trust between subordinate and supervisor; and that develop organizational citizenship behavior in employees and subsequently provoke them to do something effective and productive out of their formal job duties through their pro-social behavior, contextual performance, extra efforts, and with a good coordination (Podsakoff et al., 2000).

Further (Anit Somech & Anat Drach Zahavy, 2004) examined the term OCB within organizational context instead of individual perspective as working under organizational changing environment is become a biggest challenge for today organization where organization majorly reliance on individuals behaviors who are willing to contribute their skills and potential beyond their formal job duties towards organization success (Lee Dedrick & Smith, 1998).

Role of HR in the Development of OCB

The organization keeps on analyzing the behavior of employees which can play a major role in the accomplishment of its objectives and sustain its long term credibility. OCB is one of the critical behavior of employees which is not though included in the formal job description but become necessary for achieving the organization objectives through its social and psychological traits provided by strong HR practices including training & development, recognition program, and empowerment practices (Asim Mukhtar et al., 2012). These

HR practices are ongoing efforts to increase the capacity of individuals/employees and directly associated with the constituents of organizational citizenship behavior (Rotundo & Sackett, 2002). The requirement of effective HR practices is crucial to lead the right human capital to beat the high level of competition among present day globalization and privatization however, employee commitment, employee engagement, and (Nahid Naderi & Reza Hovieda, 2013) psychological empowerment hold an influential position in the encouragement and development of OCB (Nadeem Ahmed, Anwar Rasheed, & Khawaja Jehanzeb. 2012).

Many recent kinds of literature emphasized the relationship of human resource practices and firm performance with the mediating effect of OCB in which service quality is one of the dominant dimensions of firm performance that could have a strong impact on OCB (Dawood Babaei et al., 2012). The ongoing process of OCB organization shows the exchange relationship of its effectiveness and employee commitment towards the accomplishment of their tasks led by challenging HR practices; therefore, the more employee will engage in organizational citizenship behavior the more they would be able to deliver the quality services.

Even though various studies have been conducted to analyze the strategic role of organizational citizenship behavior with individual perspective and within the organization context but scholars haven't much focused on examining the impact of the strategic role of HR practices in the development of organizational citizenship behavior. This study therefore, aims to determine the effect of selected HR practices such as (recruitment & selection, training & development, and compensation & benefit) in the development of organizational citizenship behavior under the realm of the chemical industry.

Training & Development

Among HR practices training & development hold a predominant and significant position, where HR professionals intend to (Okpara & Wynn, 2008) analyze employee's strengths and weaknesses based on their skills, commitment, and intrinsic behavior to perform a specific task (Chughtai and Zafar, 2006). Recent studies show that training & development programs have the capacity to provide employees opportunities for advancement, this creates a sense of support and belongingness and therefore, employees reveal a strong dedication and citizenship behavior with the organization and its related tasks (Meyer & Smith, 2000).

H1: There is a significant and positive relationship between training & development and organizational citizenship behavior.

Recruitment and Selection

In the view of Nickson, Warhurst, Dutton, and Hurrell (2008) there are various issues connected with the recruitment and selection process; though they can be improved by appealing the employees with emotional commitment. The commitment may be inclined through the recruitment & selection policies and practices and it is powerfully related to the attractive communication of employees, their values, beliefs and thus ultimately increase their level of citizenship behavior (Boon, Safa & Arumugam, 2006).

H2: There is a positive and significant relationship between recruitment & selection and organizational citizenship behavior.

Compensation & Benefit

Compensation & Benefit is a sensitive practice of HR management, as it is associated with an employee's salary, pay, reward, incentives, and other allowances (Chiang & Birtch, 2011). Accordingly if employees facilitate with good remuneration package, rewards, and another benefit then he or she would definitely increase their level of commitment with the organization (Lee et al., 2006). Moreover it may help employees to raise their values and citizenship behavior towards the effective accomplishment of organization set goals.

H3: There is a significant and positive relationship between compensation & benefit and organizational citizenship behavior.

Conceptual Framework

Fig 1: The relationship between HR Practices and OCB

METHODOLOGY

Research Design:

The current study was carried out based on a quantitative research design. The aim of the current study was to determine whether the HR practices including recruitment & selection, training & development, and compensation & benefit associate with organizational citizenship behavior. Data was collected through cross sectional survey method to disseminate the questionnaire to the participants of the Pakistani chemical industry. The first portion of the questionnaire was comprised of HR practices including (recruitment & selection, training & development, and compensation & benefit) whereas the other portion of the questionnaire was comprised of organizational citizenship behavior letting in (Altruism, Courtesy, Conscientiousness, and civic virtue). Moreover descriptive research was applied to analyze the hypotheses of the subject of the study. Respondents were selected through snowball sampling method throughout the targeted area.

Population and Sample:

The population of the current study consisted of the chemical industry of Pakistan. The total of four firms from the chemical industry was included where the estimated population was being noted around 450 people. From this population 350 employees were invited or targeted to participate in the current study; however only 251 filled up questionnaires were received with all aspects. Therefore the sample size of the current study was being restricted on 251 responses where the frequency of male 200 (79.6%) and 51 female (20.3%).

Sampling Technique:

The snowball sampling has been used to assemble the data. Snowball sampling is a kind of non-probability sampling in which respondents/participants were selected through referral bases to enlarge the network of respondents.

Procedure/Data Collection

First and foremost a covering letter of permission has been transmitted accompanied with a questionnaire to the volunteers or targeted people to describe the purpose of the study as well as requested to respondents to anticipate completing the questionnaire with all aspects. Once permission was granted, questionnaires were distributed through three phases of delivery: electronic mail, referral, and hand delivery.

Instrument Development:

In the current study two instruments including HR practices and organizational citizenship behavior have been utilized whose reliability and validity have already been established.

1. HR Practices:

HR Practices was measured through an instrument having 16 items, developed by Collins & Smith, 2006 covering the major areas of HR Policies and Programs including recruitment and selection, Training and Development, Compensation & Benefit by using a five-point Likert scale.

2. Organizational Citizenship Behavior

To measure employees' OCB, the researcher used the four-dimension scale developed by Podsakoff and Mackenzie (1989). Each of four constructs—altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, and civic virtue—included items describing specific behaviors, and managers indicated their agreement on each item for each employee working for them by using a Five-point Likert scale.

Variables used in the Current Study:

There is a total of four variables used in the current study including Recruitment & Selection, Training & Development, Compensation & Benefit, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

1. **Independent Variables**___ Recruitment& Selection, Training & Development, and Compensation & Benefit were used as independent variables.
2. **Dependent Variable**___ Organizational citizenship behavior used as a dependent variable.

Data Analysis:

Data were analyzed using the statistical software package SPSS 20. The purpose of using SPSS software was to come across the detailed analysis of the relationship of proposed variables. The analysis involved Cronbach alpha which is used to check the reliability of constructs, descriptive analysis was carried out to measure the mean. Also skewness and kurtosis were examined to see whether or not data have univariate normality, correlation analysis was carried out to examine the relationship between the variables.

FINDINGS & RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics of four variables including (organizational citizenship behavior, Recruitment & Selection, Training and Development, and Compensation & Benefit) were carried out to analyze the variation among variables and make conclusions beyond the data.

Table 1

Constructs	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
OCB	3.64	0.78	-0.17	0.62
R&S	3.65	0.77	-0.26	0.54
T&D	3.54	0.62	-0.13	-0.34
C&B	3.59	0.54	0.34	-0.60

Table 1 indicates that compensation & Benefit (Mean=3.59, SD= 0.54) has the highest skewness (0.34) though the value of kurtosis is -0.60. Further, Training & Development (Mean = 3.54, SD=.62) has the lowest skewness as compared to other HR practices and its value is negative as well (-0.13). The skewness for all the items is negative except compensation & benefit. Since all the constructs are within the range of ± 3.5 , therefore it can be assumed that the data has a normal tendency (Hair Jr. et al, 2010).

Reliability

The reliability test was carried out to measure the Cronbach's alpha values to examine the internal consistency of items.

Table 2

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
OCB	0.82	16
R&S	0.70	03
T&D	0.71	09
C&B	0.69	04

Reliability of all selected items, 32 items in total, was checked through the measure of Cronbach's Alpha which was .837 whereas .70 is considered to be reliable value for the instrument (Nunnally, 1978). Further, the reliability of each individual variable is also measured where organizational citizenship behavior entailed the highest value ($\alpha=0.82$) and compensation & benefit entailed the lowest value ($\alpha=0.69$). Similarly the reliability of other constructs appears around 0.70, shows that all constructs have internal consistency and reliability of items.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is used in research to examine the strength and degree of association between two variables. Pearson Correlations r is the most used correlation coefficient, explaining the linear relations between two variables independent and dependent or X and Y (Malhotra, 2010). Correlation values lie between -1 (which indicates a strong negative relationship) and +1 (which indicates a strong positive relationship), while 0 indicates that no correlation exists. The positive and negative value indicates the direction of the correlation. When calculating the significance of correlation the sample size is very important as larger the number of respondents higher will be the significance (Bryman & Bell, 2005). Below following table 3, depict the summarized correlation results of current study variables.

Table 3

Construct	OCB	R & S	T & D	C & B
O C B	1.00			
R & S	0.34**	1.00		
T & D	0.52**	0.24	1.00	
C & B	0.24**	0.40**	0.37*	1.00

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 3 has analyzed association among all variables through correlation analysis and most of these are having a significant relationship with each other. The relationships have been measured at a 95% confidence level denoted through a single star as well as at a 99% confidence level denoted through the double star. Where the highest correlation appeared between O C B and T & D which is 52%; however the lowest correlation appeared between O C B and C & B which is 24%. Overall variables appeared as positively correlated to each other.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

The study shows that there is a strong relationship between HR practices (recruitment & selection, training & development, and compensation & benefit) and organizational citizenship behavior (Guy Pare & Michel Tremblay, 2008). Accordingly employees expect higher support and establishment of effective and well-designed HR practices in return for showing organizational citizenship behavior (Simon James Bell, 2002). Furthermore this study adds the notion that employees OCB behavior become one of the dominant facet of the

organization as it has a tendency to provoke or stimulate employees to do beyond their formal job requirement (Amir Ali Chutgai, 2008) provided by best fit HR practices. Thus, overall the stance of the current study demonstrates the positive attributes of strategic HR practices on employee citizenship behavior; in which employees and organization both may facilitate and grow toward effectiveness.

This paper has surveyed the relevant literature and then analyzed the hypotheses of the subject of the study. The study showed that there is a sound relationship that exists between strategic HR practices and organizational citizenship behavior provided by employee extra role behavior to perform their specific task in exchange for strategic HR practices. The route of HR practices including (training & development, recruitment & selection, and compensation & benefit) may express to employees that their organization encourages humanistic values, care about their well-being as well as their personal and professional development, and shows interest to trust on them (Guy Pare & Michel Tremblay, 2007). This sort of imperatives inspires employees to enhance their personal interest and contribution and ultimately demonstrate their outstanding work behavior towards the effectiveness of organizational functions (Morrison, 1996). Consequently recruitment & selection is the most crucial practice of HR management (Sumayya Begum, Sun Zehou, and Mohammad Sarker, 2014). By hypothesis 2 the process of recruitment & selection may assure a dynamic fit between the employees' capabilities and organization necessity and thus, eventually promote the employee's citizenship behavior to accomplish organizational set objectives more effectively and efficiently (Law Siew Fang & Sandra Jones, 2009). Whereas by hypothesis 2 the process of training & development has greatest influential impact in fostering employee's citizenship behavior; as training & development programs are most useful to deal with individual and group to understand and mitigate their issues and assist them in respecting each other attitude, values, and behavior (Amirtharaj, et al., 2011). Compensation is also held a significant position among HRM functions in which organizations categorize it as, a salary, rewards to motivate them to go extra-mile on performance track (Henderson, 2006). Overall current study manifested the evidence that the role of recruitment & selection, training & development, and compensation & benefit plays an important role in encouraging employee's organizational citizenship behavior.

Limitations and Implications

Two limitations were also fore grounded based on the current study. In the current study, only selected HR practices (Recruitment & Selection, Training & Development, and Compensation & Benefit) were being considered to examine the impact of organizational citizenship behavior; though other HR practices such as employee relation, health and well-being, performance appraisal etc.) Could also have been imposed a significant impact on OCB. In the future, therefore there should be a need for considering other HR practices not even only in the Pakistani Chemical industry but also under the premises of other countries to know OCB more better basis.

Another limitation was associated with its generalizability, as the current study was carried out only in one sector which is a chemical industry; however other sectors for instance manufacturing, engineering, and pharmaceutical, government agencies, and other private sectors could have been generalized the result of the study. Thus, in future studies there is a need to consider multiple sectors for better examining the relationship between HR practices and organizational citizenship behavior.

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